

The Use Of Elements Of Fashion Sustainability In The Design Of A Modern Collection In The Style Of “Denim”

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Abstract: *This article discusses the use of elements of fashion sustainability in the design of a modern collection in the style of "Denim", one of the fabrics. A designed collection, Denim style has always been popular in youth fashion and recently it has information on establishing a strong presence in collections of high fashion materials such as Denim jacket, pants, sweater and skirt.*

Keywords — fashion, costume, style, modernity, denim, collection, material, design, durability, mold resistance.

INTRODUCTION.

Denim style is always popular in youth fashion, and recently it has firmly established itself in the collections of high fashion masters. Denim jackets, shirts, and dresses most often look worn, faded, and worn. Variations of the methods of decorative design of the surface of denim 1 are diverse: it is decorated with embroidery, sequins, applications, inlay. Techniques and combinations of the design of denim material are replenished annually. Ripped jeans are still fashionable, but now the holes with the help of laser perforation form a lace-type pattern.[1]

Feminine dresses and tops, elegant jackets, and spectacular accessories destroy the idea of denim as an exclusively sporty style material. Heavy denim in dark tones combined with clear, honed lines of the cut allows you to create a modern youth image. Clothes made of light denim in light tones acquire a new semantic artistic load. Rough and heavy-looking denim actually often turns out to be soft and relatively light. Fashionable clothes combine materials of different colors and textures: light with heavy, dense with transparent, etc. A wide range of colors is characteristic: from deep saturated indigo to the palest, airy shades.

The range of denim clothing is striking in its variety: trousers with an open top, vest or tunic, shirt dress, voluminous blouse or jacket complete with tiny shorts, long coat with a mini sundress. The use of new denim processing technologies allows you to create an effect of sophistication and sophistication. A denim jacket is impregnated with amino acids to protect its owner from aging, copper threads are woven into the fabric to prevent vascular pathologies, cellulite capsules and television microscreens are embedded in clothes. No matter how capricious fashion changes, jeans, adapting to it, change beyond recognition, transforming in accordance with the fashionable demands of the time. Sometimes, because of the decor, there is little to remind you of denim.[2]

Denim dresses are winning the hearts of fashionistas more and more every year. This versatile garment is suitable for slim, plump, short, and tall. It can be worn at home and at parties. It can be appropriate both at work and for shopping.

There are a variety of models of denim dresses in fashion: cases, tunics, safaris, with a train, with a spare. There are models that fit the figure, and those that have an inflated waist. Now there are even wedding dresses made of denim. Various models are decorated with flounces, ruffles, lace, fur The style characterizes the formal and aesthetic features of objects that carry a certain content.

The style expresses a system of ideas and views, which reflects the worldview of the era. Therefore, the style can be considered a general artistic expression of the era, a reflection of the artistic experience of a person of his time. The style shows, in particular, the ideal of beauty prevailing in this historical era. Style is a concrete embodiment of emotional features and ways of thinking common to the whole culture and defining the basic principles of shaping and types of structural connections, which are the basis for the homogeneity of the subject environment at a certain historical stage.[2]

Despite the changeability of modern fashion, there are things that time has no control over. One of the most striking examples of cult classics is denim clothing, without which it is impossible to imagine any women's wardrobe. Having appeared for more than 150 years as a work uniform, practical jeans have become a true legend in the fashion industry, and now they are irreplaceable in styles all over the world. A little later, other clothes began to be sewn from denim, and the fabric firmly entered the trending TOP of famous designers due to its practicality and advantageous appearance.

Picture-1. High-rise jeans made from sustainable denim

Picture-2. Jeans planet Denim

With each season, new stylish solutions and bright details appear in denim fashion. Today, the elements of sustainability and fashion in the design of a modern collection in the style of "denim" are the most popular. Denim (denim; according to one version from the French serge de Nîmes "Neem fabric") is a durable cotton fabric with a base in which the weft passes under two or more threads of the base. This twill weave creates a diagonal ribbing that distinguishes it from cotton duk.[3]

While the predecessor of denim, known as dungaree, has been produced in India for hundreds of years, denim, as it is recognized today, was first produced in Nimes, France. Denim is available in a variety of colors, but the most common is indigo denim, in which the warp thread is dyed and the weft thread remains white. As a result of twill intertwining with the warp, blue warp threads predominate on one side of the fabric, and white weft threads predominate on the other side. Thus, jeans made from this fabric have a predominantly white color inside. Sulfur-based dyes are used to produce denim in other colors (in particular, black).[3]

Denim style has always been popular in youth fashion, and recently it has firmly established itself in collections of high fashion materials such as denim jackets, trousers, sweatshirts, skirts and dresses. Feminine dresses and tops elegant jackets and spectacular accessories destroy the idea of Denim as a material of exclusively sporty style. Heavy denim in dark tones combined with clear honed lines of the cut allows you to create a modern youth image. Clothes made of light denim in light tones acquire a new semantic artistic load. Fashionable clothes combine materials of different colors and textures. A wide range of colors is characteristic, from deep saturated indigo to the palest airy shades. Denim dresses are winning the hearts of fashionistas more and more every year. This versatile garment is suitable for slim and plump, short and tall. It can be worn at home and at parties. It can be appropriate both at work and for shopping.[4]

Picture-3. Fashionable denim dresses.

Modern fashion suggests wearing jeans even as office wear. Denim clothing is also acceptable for evening fashion black gray burgundy brown denim trousers can be worn with a guipure or digital blouse with a fur cape vest or stole.

Picture-4. Jeans combined with other clothes.

A special place in the design of denim clothing is occupied by the finishing of the denim itself, which gives it various

effects of scuffing and wear, the appearance of fabric faded in the sun, repainting and tearing. In order for denim clothes to look stylish and appropriate, it must be properly combined with other elements of the image.[4]

Proven tips from fashion designers will help you create a harmonious set based on denim:

Denim total-look is on trend. Don't be afraid to overdo it with denim items – this combination is at the peak of popularity today. Choose fashionable jeans according to your figure, complement them with a shirt or top made of a similar material. And so that the outfit does not look bland, add a drop of bright notes with the help of catchy accessories.

To make skin-tight skinny jeans look defiant, complement them with a tunic or a light blouse covering the hips. In combination with elegant sandals or stiletto heels, this image will turn out to be fragile and feminine.

An ultra-short top will look good with overstated jeans – such a tandem will visually remove a couple of centimeters in the waist and make the hips neater. And trousers with a low fit are better combined with elongated T-shirts covering the stomach.[5]

A classic navy denim skirt is easy to beat with the right top.

In combination with a polo, it forms a chic option for everyday walks, and in tandem with a thin silk or lace T-shirt - an elegant and catchy outfit for a party. To get this or that result, jeans undergo special processing, sometimes very time-consuming. The designed collection is designed for everyday wear, the materials offered correspond to the costume group. Since the developed models provide various shapes according to the degree of fit and geometric shape of the silhouette, good drapery and shape stability were taken into account when choosing the main materials.[5] The main materials for the trousers of the skirt and jacket were denim fabric with sufficient strength and shape stability. A thin cotton material with high hygroscopicity has been selected as the main material for blouses.

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